

success story

> Pilot 5: Disaster Resilience > Drought, forest fire & pest risk assessment

New information about drought risks and forest disturbances in national online portals about water issues and climate change

EIFFEL work in a pilot study on climate-related multi-hazard risks for forests in Finland has allowed to expand two existing national online portals with operational information about drought risk forecasts and long-term climate change impacts of forest disturbances. The pilot work, carried out at the Finnish Environment Institute (Syke), focused on three hazards to forests, drought, forest fires and forest pests, by combining quantitative analysis of satellite-based data, modelling and scenario applications.

Syke's own national-scale Watershed Simulation and Forecasting System (WSFS), which is used for operational flood and drought forecasting, has been further developed by improving regular forecast outputs of indicators describing drought conditions, and model evaluation has been made easier by directly linking the model to near-real-time satellite soil moisture data. Drought indicators include standardized indicators for precipitation, runoff, soil moisture and ground water for 2-3 months ahead and for different length periods (1,3, 6 and 12 months). These developments allowed to enhance the national portal about water issues, www.waterinfo.fi, with improved drought indicators and new maps of seasonal drought forecasts (See an example of the webpage directed at the general public in the screenshot below). A new drought map page with more detailed information about drought indicators has also been added to a work desk of the portal directed at water management experts.

Future simulations with the same hydrological model using climate scenarios until the end of the 21st century are also shown in a mapping tool of the national climate change portal www.climateguide.fi. The pilot work allowed to further develop this scenario mapping tool by adding a download functionality of all included climate change impact indicators, following FAIR and open data principles. Opening up of datasets about climate impact indicators can be a valuable resource for regional adaptation planning. The pilot's analysis of climate change risks from wildfire and forest pests, for which new models were developed, are planned to be added to the climateguide.fi mapping tool.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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Screenshot of operational drought forecasts from the waterinfo.fi portal
([Drought situation | Vesi.fi](http://Drought%20situation%20|%20Vesi.fi))